

Business Process Management in the Enterprise

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Abstract. *Relevance: Effective business process management helps to increase productivity, reduce costs, improve the quality of products or services, and achieve strategic goals.*

Keywords: *Business process, process optimization, and automation, process modeling (BPMN), process approach, digitalization, reengineering, process monitoring, business process analysis, bottlenecks.*

The modern period is characterized by increased attention to process-oriented principles of enterprise management. From the point of view of optimization, the essence of the process approach lies in finding effective methods for regulating business processes in companies and managing its resources. In this regard, the development of management methods based on which management is considered as a strictly regulated, step-by-step approach to regulating business processes at an enterprise, taking into account the mobility and sustainability of development, is of exceptional importance. This is especially important for ensuring the effective development of business structures characterized by increased risk, fraught with their bankruptcy and catastrophe.

The various development programs adopted today do not fully ensure effective management and do not reflect the structuring of business processes and their management in relation to the conditions of the competitive business environment.

The process approach allows focusing on the most "painful points" that are symptoms of the onset of unstable development of the enterprise and finding an acceptable level of resolving contradictions that arise in the market environment. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account that the process approach is inseparable from the technical and technological component of the market, and its effectiveness is achieved by finding optimal solutions throughout the entire production cycle. This is achieved through the mechanism of the process-oriented principle of improving the quality of management, which always makes its way through the adoption of optimal decisions in the field of the quality management system.

The widespread introduction of the process management method is an inevitable and objectively necessary response to changes in the economy, competitive conditions, and changes in technology and engineering.

The process approach involves a management mechanism that fundamentally changes the nature of the development of economic relations, based on the resource component, which allows one to concentrate on obtaining the final result and sharply reduce specific costs while simultaneously improving the quality of production.

The implementation of the process approach in management is impossible without the broad active participation of all personnel in this process, the involvement of literally every employee. At the same time, the organization must implement a whole range of measures for the corresponding staged implementation of the process approach with the formation of business processes designed to

improve the efficiency and quality of the enterprise.

The relevance of the topic is determined by the fact that the business process affects various levels of the social reproduction system and at the same time creates the preconditions for management in times of crisis, which requires finding effective solutions for forecasting various scenarios at all levels of the economic hierarchy.

The options for managing business processes at an enterprise can be very diverse; economic theory has a rich arsenal of theoretical and methodological tools. In this regard, it is important to find preventive measures to regulate business processes at enterprises. It is from this angle that we sought to consider the implementation of the process approach in enterprise management, especially in relation to the competitive business environment.

The degree of scientific development of the problem. The scientific basis for the study was the works and papers of both foreign authors devoted to business process management, including those considering the problems of consistency and efficiency: K. Hein, F. Gunyar, T. Davenport, E. Deming, J. Kelly, M. Robson, T. Sarson, D. Ullah, H. van Hamnege, R. Hammer, D. Harrington, J. Champy, A. Scheer, J. Sheldrake, K. Esseling, and Russian scientists and practitioners: N.M. Abdikeev, A.M. Gadzhinsky, T.P. Danko, V.A. Ivlev, G.N. Kalyanov, D.A. Kiselev, V.G. Medynsky, E.G. Oykman, E.V. Popov, T.V. Popona, Yu.F. Telnov, A.V. Tyutyunnik.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the work also included the works of both world classics of quality management: E. Deming, J. Juran, K. Ishikawa, F. Crosby, G. Taguchi, A. Feigenbaum, W. Shewhart, and Russian scientists and practitioners: V. N. Azarov, B. V. Boytsov, V. A. Vasiliev, S. D. Tal'enkova, A. V. Kvitko, V. A. Lapidus, V. M. Mishin, A. N. Rekshinsky, V. A. Shvandar, Yu. V. Shlenov and others, devoted to various aspects of quality management. These scientific works cover individual issues related to the formation of a quality management system, but they do not cover issues of using a quality management system within an enterprise related to the development of the organization's business processes.

With a large number of works devoted to the process approach itself and the implementation of business processes, as well as the quality management system at the enterprise, there remains a need for scientific development of a set of theoretical, methodological and practical problems of substantiating the stages of implementation of business processes at the enterprise, creating a mechanism for assessing the quality of the implementation of the process approach (indicators of efficiency and effectiveness). In theoretical terms, the study of the process of formation and substantiation of the process approach in conjunction with the quality management system at the enterprise is of interest. In the methodological and practical aspect, the development of methods for the formation of business processes at various enterprises is of great importance - both in corporate enterprises, including business units, and in simple enterprises.

Insufficient study, relevance, theoretical and practical significance of the problem of using the process approach, formation and structuring of business processes in the conditions of a specific enterprise and especially in the conditions of a quality management system, as well as issues of assessing the effectiveness and quality of process management determined the choice of the topic, the purpose of the study and its objectives.

The subject of the study is economic relations arising from the process approach to managing business processes at an enterprise, and its object is enterprises where the enterprise business process management system is being implemented or operates under the process approach.

The purpose of the study is to develop methodological foundations and practical recommendations for the formation of a process approach to managing business processes at an enterprise adequate to the modern quality management system and an organizational mechanism for ensuring the functioning of business processes at the enterprise.

The purpose of the study is specified in the following tasks:

➤ to analyze the development of scientific views on functional, process management, to clarify the

definitions of “business process” and “business process reengineering”;

- to consider and compare functional and process management and identify the advantages of the process approach in enterprise management;
- identify the features of the logistics approach to managing business processes at the enterprise;
- improve the methodological approach to choosing a business process management model at an enterprise;
- to form a process approach as the basis of a quality management system applicable to the management of business processes at an enterprise;
- propose a structure for managing business processes at the enterprise in accordance with the requirements of the QMS and the process approach;
- develop a mechanism to ensure the quality of business process management at the enterprise;
- to propose an algorithm for the effective implementation of the enterprise development strategy, developed on the basis of the integration of reengineering and the quality management system.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study was formed by fundamental scientific developments of foreign and Russian scientists and specialists in the field of process management and business process reengineering.

The regulatory framework for the study, as applied to the problem under consideration, consists of legislative acts and other regulatory documents of Russian government bodies, information published in scientific publications, in the periodical press, information from enterprises, and materials from international and Russian scientific conferences on the problem under consideration.

The methodological basis of the work is the dialectical method, the system approach, the methods of economic analysis and synthesis. The use of dialectics makes it possible to take into account the interrelation of phenomena, their contradictory nature, and variability. The dialectical method assumes the use of analysis and synthesis, the method "from the abstract to the concrete", historical and logical, induction and deduction when studying economic processes and phenomena.

To solve the tasks set in the work, economic and statistical methods, methods of modeling economic processes and analysis of financial activities were also used.

The empirical basis of the study consisted of materials from round tables, Russian and international scientific conferences, journal articles and materials from business practice characterizing the production and business activities of corporations, financial and industrial groups, regulatory documents, Rosstat data, statistical and other information sources.

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